

Education in the eye of the storm: A bibliometric review of research on global crises and their impact on Southern African education (2000–2024)

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Abstract

This research article provides an in-depth bibliometric review of the literature on educational impacts during the period from 2000 to 2024. The analysis specifically concentrates on global crises and their implications for education, with a special emphasis on the Southern African region. Through an integration of epistemic injustice, critical pedagogy, and social justice into the search strategy employed in the article, this research provides an understanding of how various crises—including pandemics, wars, economic recessions, and environmental disasters—have intensified disparities in education and posed significant challenges to the resilience of education systems. The article surveys 5,511 publications and draws on a rigorous methodological approach to examine the volumes, growth trajectories, dominant themes, and collaboration networks of literature within the field of education research. It identifies key contributors and identifies areas where further research is required. The results indicate a need for a greater focus on the human aspects of crises, highlighting the critical need for policies and approaches to education that prioritise equity, inclusion, and resilience. The study provides specific suggestions for policymakers, educators, and researchers to create education systems that could effectively change and adapt during times of crisis, thus ensuring equitable and quality education for everyone. This analysis not only makes a valuable contribution to the scholarly debate on education during periods of crisis, but also offers practical perspectives for envisioning different approaches to research, teaching, and learning in order to foster a more equitable and resilient future.

Keywords: bibliometric review, education impact, global crises, Southern African education, epistemic injustice, critical pedagogy, social justice

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Introduction

Global crises, such as conflicts, pandemics, environmental disasters, and economic recessions, have profoundly affected educational systems worldwide, over the past two decades. These crises have exacerbated pre-existing inequalities, disrupted education, and exposed vulnerabilities—particularly in the Global South and Southern Africa (Menon & Motala, 2022; Ojo & Lorenzini, 2021; Ojo & Onwuegbuzie, 2020; Ojo et al., 2023; Swart et al., 2022). The pursuit of social justice, equity, and inclusion in education has been significantly hindered, disproportionately affecting marginalised and vulnerable populations (Ainscow, 2020; Batisai et al., 2022; Govender et al., 2020).

This paper presents a rigorous bibliometric analysis of literature on educational impact during global crises between 2000 and 2024. By examining trends, patterns, and gaps, the analysis aims to inform policy, practice, and future research. The overarching question was: “What developments have occurred in the academic discourse on education during global crises between 2000 and 2024, and what knowledge can be gained to reimagine research, teaching, and learning in the Southern African region?” The paper addresses four specific research questions:

1. What is the volume, growth trajectory, and pattern of literature on the impact of global crises on education from 2000 to 2024, and how do the trends in Southern Africa compare to the global landscape?
2. What are the dominant themes and their interconnections, which have evolved in educational research during global crises?
3. Who are the top contributing authors, institutions, and countries in the field of educational impact research during global crises, how have the contributions from South African researchers and institutions evolved over time, and are there any gaps or opportunities for further research?
4. What are the nature and dynamics of collaborations among leading countries and institutions in educational impact research during crises from 2000 to 2024?

This bibliometric analysis contributes to the development of resilient and equitable education systems by offering a critical understanding of social justice, epistemic justice, and the possibility of redefining education during crises. The findings have implications for future research, policy, and practice within the Southern African context, highlighting approaches to building adaptive and transformative education systems.

Impact of global crises on education: A review through the perspectives of epistemic injustice, critical pedagogy, and social justice

This section untangles the complex web that crises have woven around the educational landscape, particularly within the Southern African context. Drawing upon theoretical frameworks such as Fricker’s epistemic injustice, Freire’s critical pedagogy, and Fraser’s social justice, it illuminates how crises have disrupted educational continuity and deepened pre-existing inequities. The section

offers a chronology of major global crises from 2000 to 2024, and concludes by presenting how these crises have specifically impacted education systems in Southern Africa.

Crises are disruptions with significant global impact affecting the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including SDG 4 on quality education. Fricker (2007) articulated epistemic injustice as a wrong done to someone in their capacity as a knower, and which is magnified during crises when marginalised voices are silenced. Freire's (1970/2005, 2020) critical pedagogy emphasised education's role in challenging injustices, and Fraser (2009) framed social justice in terms of participation, distribution, and recognition.

Table 1 provides a succinct summary of 14 key global crises from 2000 to 2024, and their impacts on education. These crises have resulted in reduced education funding, school closures, displacement of students and teachers, worsening inequalities, and redirection of resources. The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly disturbed the education sector, impacting more than 1.6 billion students, globally (UNESCO, 2020).

Table 1
Global crises and their impact on education (2000–2024)

Years	Crisis	Education impact
2000–2002	Dot-com bubble burst	Reduced education funding; slowed technological integration
2001	September 11 terrorist attacks	Reduced student mobility; funds diverted to security
2002–2004	SARS outbreak	School closures in Asia; disrupted learning
2003–2011	Iraq War	Displaced students and teachers; diverted resources
2004	Indian Ocean earthquake and tsunami	Destroyed schools; set back education in region
2005	Hurricane Katrina	Damaged schools; displaced students; revealed inequities
2000–ongoing	Israeli-Palestinian conflict	Reduced quality; funds diverted to security; student/teacher stress
2007–2008	Global food crisis	Reduced school attendance due to food insecurity
2007–2008	Global financial crisis	Education budget cuts; reduced access and quality
2010–2012	European debt crisis	Austerity measures reduced education opportunities
2010s–present	Climate crisis	Infrastructure damage; migration; need for adaptation
2014–2016	Ebola epidemic	Widespread school closures in West Africa
2019–present	COVID-19 pandemic	Largest education disruption in history; remote learning
2022–present	Russo-Ukrainian War	Higher costs; reduced digital access; impacted vulnerable areas

Figure 1 shows the interrelated nature of these 14 global crises and their cumulative impact on education. The analysis emphasises the necessity for resilient and adaptable education systems,

requiring investment in infrastructure, digital technologies, teacher education, and assistance for marginalised communities. Addressing underlying factors such as climate change, conflict, and inequality is imperative for establishing a stable atmosphere for education.

Figure 1

Chronological overview of global crises and their impact on education (2000–2024)

In the Southern African context, the region has exhibited greater vulnerability to the crises, exacerbating pre-existing difficulties in education systems and infrastructures (Rudling et al., 2023). The economic difficulties following the global food crisis have imposed challenges on families in prioritising education (World Food Programme, 2022), resulting in increased student attrition and compromised educational quality (Nikolaidis et al., 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic intensified educational disparities (Haelermans et al., 2022) and exposed the digital divide. Southern African nations must invest in adaptable, inclusive, and resilient educational systems to promote peace and sustainable development in the region.

Data collection and methodology

Dataset collection

The data for this paper were collected through Scopus, a comprehensive and authoritative database of peer-reviewed papers. The search strategy was informed by the *Southern African Review of Education (SARE)*'s call for papers on “Re-imagining Research and Teaching and Learning During Times of Crises,” which mentioned seven distinct terms and themes related to crisis: COVID-19 pandemic, crisis of environment, humanitarian crises, economic crises, and instability’s educational impact, social-emotional detriments, and educational inequities. The search string used was:

(“crisis” OR “Covid-19” OR “environmental” OR “humanitarian” OR “economic”) AND (“education” OR “teaching” OR “learning” OR “inequities”) AND (“research” OR “policy analysis” OR “discourse” OR “methods”) AND (“justice” OR “equity” OR “care” OR “empathy” OR “trust”) OR (“resilience” OR “quality education”) OR (“Africa” OR “Global South”)

Dataset pre-processing and refinement

The study conducted a preliminary search on February 20, 2024, and a final retrieval on March 21, 2024, yielding 59,890 documents. To ensure relevance and manageability, a systematic pre-processing protocol was employed, resulting in 5,511 documents pertinent to the research scope.

Filtration criteria included: temporal scope (2000–2024), subject areas (social sciences, and arts and humanities), document types (peer-reviewed articles, book chapters, reviews, editorial books, and conference proceedings), and keywords (20 terms reflecting multidimensional aspects of crises). The corpus was confined to English-language publications. The PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses) flow diagram (Figure 2) presents the studies included.

Figure 2
Processing of document eligibility based on PRISMA guideline

Data analysis strategies

Initial data analysis using Scopus provided a descriptive breakdown of the 5,511 documents. Further analysis using VOSViewer included performance analysis and science mapping the bibliometric assessments. Performance analysis metrics included publication volume and citation frequency. Science mapping techniques like citation analysis, bibliographic coupling, and network

analysis were used to explore research components' interplay and structural linkages. Table 2 outlines the organisational framework for the findings and discussion section.

Table 2
Bridging analysis and insight in educational crisis research

Findings & discussion section	Title	Research questions	Analysis type
1	Research landscape: An overview of literature on educational impacts of global crises (2000–2024)	RQ1: Volume, growth, and patterns of literature on educational impacts of global crises	Performance analysis
2	Publication trends: Examining growth and types of publications (2000–2024)	RQ1: Volume, growth, and patterns of literature on educational impacts of global crises	Performance analysis
3	Key contributors: Mapping authors, institutions, and countries in educational impact research during crises	RQ3: Top contributing authors, institutions, and countries in educational impact research	Performance analysis
4	Collaborative networks: Analysing partnerships among leading countries and institutions (2000–2024)	RQ4: Nature and dynamics of collaborations among leading countries and institutions	Science mapping
5	Influential journals: A bibliometric perspective on top publications shaping the discourse on education during crises	(Supports all research questions by identifying influential journals)	Performance analysis
6	Thematic landscape: Exploring dominant themes and interconnections in educational research during global crises	RQ2: Dominant themes and their interconnections in educational research during global crises	Science mapping

Findings and discussion

This section, as previously outlined, unveils the results of the bibliometric analysis and contextualises the findings within the evolving academic dialogue on education amidst global crises between 2000 and 2024. It explores the progress and insights gleaned, with an eye to re-envisioning research, teaching, and learning in the Southern African context.

1. Research landscape: Volume, growth, and patterns of literature on educational impacts of global crises (2000–2024)

Analysis of the quantity of publications and the trajectory of growth between 2000 and 2024 provides an in-depth overview of yearly patterns in research productivity within the field encompassed by the dataset. Through an analysis of the annual publication count, significant insights can be obtained regarding the progression and transformation of the research domain during the designated timeframe. The purpose of this section is to emphasise important patterns of growth and noteworthy observations, providing insight into the dynamics of the field being studied. To conduct the analysis, a summary of the yearly publication counts from 2000 to 2024

was generated through Scopus as earlier presented. This allowed for a succinct presentation of the trend, and facilitated observation of any significant variations or patterns in the number of publications throughout the period. The findings demonstrate a complex pattern of growth, marked by discrete stages of progress (see Figure 3).

Figure 3
Growth trajectory of publication volume from 2000 to 2024

Between the years 2000 and 2019, the dataset demonstrates a consistent upward trend in the annual count of publications. The number of publications published annually experienced a notable increase from a modest 24 in 2000 to a respectable 229 in 2019, suggesting a sustained development in research productivity over this period. The slow growth indicates a persistent interest and commitment to the field as scholars persistently investigated and enhanced the current knowledge base.

Nevertheless, the year 2020 represented a significant milestone in the trajectory of progress. Since the beginning of 2020, there has been a notable surge in the quantity of publications, with the count almost doubling from 229 in 2019 to a remarkable 413 in 2020. The marked increase persisted without interruption—as seen by the publication count reaching 849 in 2021, 1,033 in 2022, and ultimately reaching an impressive peak of 1,100 in 2023. The abrupt and substantial increase in the number of publications indicates a notable change in the research environment during this time, indicating a heightened degree of interest, investment, and activity in the field. It should be emphasised that the figure for 2024 (211 publications) is incomplete data because 2024 is the current year. As the number of publications increases throughout the course of the year, it is anticipated that the final count will rise, potentially mirroring the rising trajectory observed in previous years.

The dataset has a growth trend that depicts a research ecosystem that is both increasing and

dynamic. The continual growth observed between 2000 and 2019 signifies a steady progress in the field of study, which laid the groundwork for the future increase in the number of publications. The significant surge starting from 2020 is especially remarkable because it indicates a convergence of variables that have stimulated research activity in the field. These aspects may encompass worldwide occurrences, progress in the domain, augmented research funding, or improved partnership prospects. Additional examination of the precise factors contributing to this expansion would yield useful perspectives on the fundamental mechanisms influencing the research environment.

In summary, analysis of the number of publications and the trend of growth between 2000 and 2024 demonstrates a notable increase in research productivity in the field encompassed by the dataset. The research landscape demonstrates a dynamic and developing nature, as evidenced by the consistent growth witnessed between 2000 and 2019, followed by a significant increase from 2020 onwards. Although the available data for the year 2024 are limited, the general pattern indicates a sustained level of interest and investment in the field of research. The present research provides a basis for subsequent investigation into the various causes that contributed to this expansion, thus facilitating a more comprehensive understanding of the evolution and prospective trajectories in the field. As scholars and individuals with vested interests negotiate this dynamic environment, the knowledge acquired from this analysis could provide valuable guidance for making strategic choices, allocating resources, and determining research objectives. Ultimately, these insights could contribute to the progress of knowledge and innovation in the field.

2. Trends in publication types and growth (2000–2024)

This section focuses on examining the trends and distribution of different types of documents published as a body of knowledge between 2000 and 2024. The article analyses the data by year and document type, and tracks the frequency with which each type appeared annually in order to understand the changes in the academic publishing landscape (see Figure 4).

I found that journal articles were the most common publication type throughout the years, emphasising their crucial role in sharing research. From 2020, I observed a significant increase in reviews and conference papers, indicating a shift towards synthesising research findings and fostering community engagement through conferences. There was also a slight rise in book chapter publications after 2010, peaking in 2022, which suggests a growing interest in offering deeper, topic-specific insights in edited volumes.

The years 2020 to 2024 marked a notable surge in all publication types, especially articles and reviews, pointing to their continued importance in research dissemination. Although conference papers and book chapters also increased, they did not grow as much as articles and reviews. It is worth noting that the data for 2024 are incomplete because the year had not ended at the time of this analysis. Although articles and reviews remain prominent, there is a temporary dip in conference papers and book chapters for 2024, which should be viewed cautiously until the year's full data are available.

Figure 4
Trends in publication types and growth from 2000 to 2024

These findings highlight a dynamic evolution in academic publishing, with a sustained preference for articles but growing interest in reviews, conference engagements, and in-depth book chapters. This evolving trend suggests that the academic community should adapt their publication strategies in order to stay ahead, ensuring that research contributions are diverse, relevant, and impactful.

3. Key players: Top contributing authors, institutions, and countries in educational impact research during global crises

This section incorporates both a table and an overlay visualisation to present the major contributors, affiliations, and geographical trends in the literature, comparing Southern Africa with global contributions. By integrating VOSViewer for the bibliometric analysis, the minimum number of documents and citations threshold for authors to be included in the Top 10 list were established as four and 15, respectively. Only 10 of the 19,652 authors fulfilled these criteria (see Table 3).

The primary contributors are authors from Europe (namely Germany and the United Kingdom), Asia (including Singapore), Australia, and the United States. In terms of citation count and h-index, Stefan Sieber from Germany holds the highest position with 525 citations, while Sarah Curtis from the United Kingdom follows closely with 279 citations and an h-index of 27. Jennifer Cleland, an author with institutional affiliation in Singapore, possesses the highest h-index of 52, garnering a total of 71 citations across four articles. Patricia Eadie and Penny Levickis from

Australia have garnered a total of 69 citations each, accompanied by h-indexes of 34 and 19, respectively. South Africa exhibits a significant presence in the academic community, as evidenced by the inclusion of Glenda Kruss (188 citations, h-index 27), Tholang Mokhele (28 citations, h-index 13), and Katijah Khoza-Shangase (15 citations, h-index 25) in the top 10 authors. Nevertheless, the citation counts, and h-indexes of these scholars tend to be somewhat lower compared to their counterparts from other countries. The visualisation overlay (Figure 5) indicates that the highly cited works of South African authors are primarily concentrated in the years 2016–2018. This suggests that there is potential for more recent and influential research to come from the country in this field.

Table 3
Top 10 most cited authors

Full name	Affiliation	Number of publications	Total citations	h-index
Stefan Sieber	Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg, Germany & Faculty of Life Sciences, Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Berlin, Germany	4	525	37
Sarah Curtis	Queen Mary College, University of London, London, UK	4	279	27
Glenda Kruss	Centre for Science, Technology and Innovation Indicators, Human Sciences Research Council, 116–118 Buitengracht Street, Cape Town 8000, South Africa	4	188	27
Jennifer Cleland	Lee Kong Chian School of Medicine, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore, Singapore	4	71	52
Patricia Eadie	Melbourne Graduate School of Education, University of Melbourne, Melbourne, Australia	4	69	34
Penny Levickis	Melbourne Graduate School of Education, University of Melbourne, Melbourne, Australia, & Genetics, Murdoch Children's Research Institute, Parkville, Australia	4	69	19
Sok Ying Liaw	Alice Lee Centre for Nursing Studies, Yong Loo Lin School of Medicine, National University of Singapore, Singapore, Singapore	4	40	38
Tholang Mokhele	Geospatial Analytics, eResearch Knowledge Centre, Human Sciences Research Council, Pretoria, South Africa	4	28	13
Usama Bilal	Urban Health Collaborative, Drexel University, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, USA & Epidemiology and Biostatistics, Drexel University, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, USA	4	18	34
Katijah Khoza-Shangase	Department of Audiology, Faculty of Humanities, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa	4	15	25

The overlay visualisation offers supplementary understanding regarding the temporal distribution of the scholarship produced by these significant authors. Stefan Sieber and Jennifer Cleland have

publications concentrated within the 2018–2020 range (green), as indicated by the colour coding. In contrast, Sarah Curtis, Patricia Eadie, and Glenda Kruss have published works that are older and have received a significant number of citations, mainly during the period of 2016 to 2018 (blue/green). However, some authors, such as Patricia Eadie, show recent activity in the 2022 range (yellow), highlighting their continued influence in the field.

Figure 5

Overlay visualisation of nine of the top 10 authors

In summary, this bibliometric study, augmented by the utilisation of tabular data and VOSViewer overlay visualisation, provides insights into the global dispersion of significant authors, their citation effects, and the temporal patterns observed in their extensively referenced publications. The overlay visualisation offers supplementary understanding regarding the temporal distribution of the scholarship produced by these significant authors. Stefan Sieber and Jennifer Cleland have publications concentrated within the 2018–2020 range (green), as indicated by the colour coding. In contrast, Sarah Curtis shows publications in the earlier range (blue, 2016–2018).

Notably, the South African authors—Khoza-Shangase, Mokhele, and Kruss—along with Bilal and Eadie, have the most recent publications, falling within the 2020–2022 range (yellow). This

suggests an increasing and recent contribution from South African researchers and others to this field of study. Although South Africa has a position among the leading contributors, there exists potential for further development in terms of citation effect and the production of more recent, highly important works when compared to their counterparts from other areas.

4. Collaboration dynamics: Nature and evolution of partnerships among leading countries and institutions (2000–2024)

This section presents the collaboration patterns over the period 2000–2024 amongst the top 10 countries across the world to elucidate the landscape of global scholarly collaboration. To do this, a rigorous selection methodology was implemented. The criteria for inclusion in this article were determined by two primary quantitative thresholds: a minimum of 107 documents and at least 20 citations per country. These benchmarks were meticulously selected to filter for substantial scholarly output and impact, ensuring that only the most prolific and influential research landscapes were considered. Of a pool of 251 countries, only 10 countries met these stringent parameters, thus forming the cohort for further analysis (see Table 4). South Africa, with its 616 documents and 6,346 citations, not only surpassed the set thresholds but also demonstrated significant international research engagement, as evidenced by its robust total link strength of 151. This positioning underscores South Africa's pivotal role in the global knowledge exchange network.

Table 4

Top 10 countries by number of documents, citations, and total link strength

Country	Citations	Documents	Total link strength
United States	36,671	1,856	334
United Kingdom	14,853	718	296
Canada	8,140	383	170
Australia	7,394	348	150
South Africa	6,346	616	151
Netherlands	3,121	115	74
Spain	2,381	134	40
Germany	2,175	153	54
China	2,072	164	77
India	2,000	164	80

Upon satisfying the selection criteria, the top 10 countries representing a spectrum of global regions were delineated for a more granular investigation of their collaborative ties. These nations, spanning continents from North America to Asia, underscore a diverse yet interconnected scholarly ecosystem. Notably, within this constellation of intellectual synergy, South Africa stands

as the sole representative of the Southern African region. This highlights a geographic imbalance in global research collaboration, underscoring the need for increased integration of various other regions to foster a more equitable knowledge-sharing platform. The data reveal that while collaboration is indeed vibrant among these 10 nations, it is imperative to acknowledge and address the underrepresentation of entire regions in the global research network.

The resulting visualisation from the bibliometric review (Figure 6) provides a dynamic representation of the scholarly connections among the selected countries over the period from 2018 to 2021. The network graph is a testament to the intricate web of academic interactions, with the United States assuming a central node, indicative of its extensive document production and citation impact. The temporal colour gradient applied to the linkages affords a nuanced understanding of the evolution of these connections over time. It is apparent that collaboration is not static; it flourishes and morphs, reflecting shifts in research priorities, funding landscapes, and geopolitical influences. The prominence of South Africa within this visualisation signifies its growing research stature and the pivotal role it plays in channelling knowledge within and beyond its continental confines. The visual map thus serves not only as a retrospective analysis but also as a clarion call for proactive strategies to cultivate a more diverse and inclusive global research network.

Figure 6

A temporal network visualisation of global research collaboration

5. Influential voices: A bibliometric analysis of top journals shaping the discourse on education during crises

The bibliometric analysis of the top academic sources by documents and citations provides valuable insights into the influential journals shaping the discourse around re-imagining research, teaching, and learning during times of crises, as called for by *SARE*. The criteria for selecting the top journals were based on the total link strength, which measures the citation connections between sources. Table 5 shows the 10 sources that were chosen from a dataset of 1,800 academic sources, focusing on those with the greatest total link strength.

Table 5

Top journals by impact factor, citations, documents, and total link strength

Journal	Impact factor	Citations	Documents	Total link strength
Social Science and Medicine	5.4	8,128	170	1
Sustainability	3.9	3,704	282	3
BMC Medical Education	3.9	2,393	147	14
Academic Medicine	5.354	1,470	68	2
Nurse Education Today	2.533	1,442	54	2
Journal of Surgical Education	2.9	1,281	38	7
Medical Teacher	3.65	1,061	36	13
Medical Education	7.5	921	35	5
Human Resources for Health	4.5	843	41	1
Journal of Education and Health Promotion	1.4	90	36	0

An examination of the citation counts in Table 5 reveals the relative influence and impact of key journals in the field of education during crises. Leading the list is *Social Science and Medicine* with the highest citation count, indicating its central role in the citation network. Its substantial number of documents and citations suggest a significant contribution to understanding the social dimensions of health and education during crises. Close behind are *Sustainability* and *BMC Medical Education*, also demonstrating strong document counts. These journals are well positioned to address *SARE*'s themes of sustainability in education policy and innovative pedagogies in health professions education.

Other notable inclusions are *Academic Medicine*, *Nurse Education Today*, and *Journal of Surgical Education*, which collectively represent key platforms for exploring the impact of crises on medical and nursing education, as well as the importance of care, empathy, and equity in educational practices. *Human Resources for Health* and *Journal of Education and Health*

Promotion, although lower in link strength, offer unique perspectives on critical issues highlighted by *SARE*, such as the role of academia in social justice and the promotion of health through education.

Figure 7 visualises the academic journal citation network by setting minimum thresholds of 35 documents and 50 citations for a source to be included. This figure showcases a diverse range of journals across disciplines such as medical education, sustainability, social science, and health resources. The selection criteria and resulting connections illustrate the interdisciplinary nature of research that aligns with *SARE*'s interest in boundary-crossing research.

The network diagram in Figure 7 visualises the interconnections among these top journals, revealing a rich tapestry of knowledge exchange. The centrality of *Social Science and Medicine* and *Sustainability* with their strong citation links to multiple other journals underscores the pivotal role of interdisciplinary research in informing educational responses to crises. *BMC Medical Education* also shows significant connections, particularly with *Medical Education* and *Medical Teacher*, highlighting the important contributions of medical education research in this field.

Figure 7

Academic journal citation network: Impact and interconnectivity

6. Thematic evolution: Dominant themes and interconnections in educational research during global crises

This section has been structured into six sub-sections, each focusing on a specific aspect of the thematic analysis. The first sub-section delves into the methodology employed, followed by an examination of the top keywords and their significance. The third sub-section explores the thematic domains and keyword clusters, and the fourth investigates the interplay and interdependencies of these thematic domains. The fifth discusses the implications for sustainable and equitable education and, lastly, the sixth sub-section provides integrative insights on the thematic landscape.

Methodology: Keyword analysis using VOSViewer

The preceding sections provided a comprehensive review of the research landscape, key authors in the field, and the dynamics of collaboration in the field of educational impact research during global emergencies and disruptions covering the years 2000 to 2024. Building on that groundwork, this section of this bibliometric review, informed by VOSViewer data, critically examines scholarly discourse across two decades, unearthing the predominant themes and their interconnections through an analysis of keywords, their occurrences, and total link strengths.

VOSViewer software was used to analyse 5,511 publications generated from Scopus, revealing a total of 19,886 keywords. To identify the top 20 keywords, a threshold was set in VOSViewer requiring each keyword to have a minimum occurrence of 326. Based on this criterion, VOSViewer calculated the total strength of the co-occurrence links between each of the 20 keywords and all other keywords. This in-depth quantitative analysis, performed across the entire volume of publications, resulted in the data presented by VOSViewer, highlighting the most prominent and interconnected keywords in the field. The data generated are presented in Table 6, and Figure 8 (next sub-section) presents a network graph of keyword co-occurrence to visualise the interconnections of the keywords based on the strength of the co-occurrence.

Table 6
Quantitative analysis of keyword frequency and interrelationship in education research (2000–2024)

Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
Human	1,883	8,674
COVID-19	1,757	4,168
Education	1,605	4,720
Humans	1,454	6,913
Article	1,056	5,162
Female	865	4,917
Male	729	4,296
Pandemic	682	3,170
Adult	635	3,763
Learning	531	1,521
Pandemics	434	2,447
South Africa	420	582
Resilience	389	459
Medical education	388	1,858
United States	380	1,597
Equity	375	406

Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
Social justice	365	404
Sustainable development	358	263
Africa	338	378
Coronavirus disease 2019	327	1,978

Top keywords and their significance

The keyword analysis using VOSViewer identified the most prominent and interconnected keywords in the field of educational research during global crises. This sub-section delves into these top keywords and their significance in understanding the key themes and priorities that have shaped the research landscape from 2000 to 2024.

Figure 8

Network graph of keyword co-occurrence in education research during global crises

The keyword table (Table 6) provides a solid starting point for this section’s thematic analysis. It helps to understand which themes are most important by looking at how often they appear, and how strongly they are connected to other keywords. The keyword, “Human,” stands above the rest. This suggests that people are at the very heart of educational research and publications, especially when the impact of major crises like the COVID-19 pandemic is considered. It is evident from this analysis that these global challenges have put a spotlight on the human experience and how it shapes the way we teach, learn, and study. Figure 8 further illustrates the network graph of keyword co-occurrence in education research during global crises.

Thematic domains and keyword clusters

On examining the keyword table and the network graph of keyword co-occurrence, an intricate web of thematic priorities and their dynamic interplay (with the keyword “Human” at the core) reveals six overarching thematic domains: (1) research and demography, (2) health and pandemic, (3) education and learning, (4) socio-political responses, (5) geographic and institutional focus, and (6) research nature and publication. Tables 7 to 12 present how these themes have been arrived at, especially using the network graph to further examine the co-occurrence in the coherent clusters of thoughts through the keywords.

Table 7

Theme 1: Research and demography

Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
Human	1,883	8,674
Humans	1,454	6,913
Female	865	4,917
Male	729	4,296
Adult	635	3,763

Table 8

Theme 2: Health and pandemic

Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
COVID-19	1,757	4,168
Pandemic	682	3,170
Pandemics	434	2,447
Coronavirus disease 2019	327	1,978

Table 9

Theme 3: Education and learning

Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
Education	1,605	4,720
Learning	531	1,521
Medical education	388	1,858

Table 10

Theme 4: Socio-political responses

Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
Resilience	389	459
Equity	375	406
Social justice	365	404
Sustainable development	358	263

Table 11

Theme 5: Geographic and institutional focus

Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
South Africa	420	582
Africa	338	378
United States	380	1,597

Table 12

Theme 6: Research nature and publication

Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
Article	1,056	5,162

Each theme, from “Research and Demography” to “Research Nature and Publication,” represents a collection of scholarly focus, with specific keywords narrating the story of change and continuity.

Interplay and interdependencies of thematic domains

The interplay between themes, such as “Health and Pandemic” influencing “Education and Learning,” and “Socio-Political Responses” intertwining with “Geographic and Institutional Focus,” underscores the complex interdependencies that shape the educational landscape. By

aligning these thematic findings with the goals of sustainable and equitable education, this bibliometric review is insightful to guiding stakeholders to embrace a proactive and resilient approach to education in the face of future crises. See the Figure 9 for a presentation of the complex interplay of these themes.

Figure 9

A graphical synthesis of inter-thematic linkages in education research

Implications for sustainable and equitable education

By weaving these clusters into the analytical narrative, this bibliometric review presents a comprehensive and compelling argument that reflects the multifaceted nature of education research during crises. It highlights the interplay between individual experiences, health impacts, pedagogical changes, socio-political actions, localised contexts, and research practices. This not only reinforces the call for a multi-dimensional understanding of crises in education but also underscores the complex interdependencies that define the field's response to unprecedented challenges.

The academic journal citation network illustrated in Figure 10 provides a visual representation of

the impact and interconnectivity of top journals in advancing the research agenda set forth by *SARE*. By showcasing the diverse disciplinary perspectives and critical conversations fostered by these publications, Figure 10 highlights their vital role in charting a path towards a more resilient, equitable, and socially just educational future, which aligns with the implications for sustainable and equitable education.

Figure 10

Academic journal citation network: Impact and interconnectivity

Integrative insights on the thematic landscape

In concluding this section, this bibliometric analysis of the thematic evolution in educational research during global crises from 2000 to 2024 provides a compelling case for the significance of top journals in advancing the research agenda set forth by *SARE*. By employing advanced analytical tools like VOSViewer, this study has unveiled a complex tapestry of interconnected themes, highlighting the multifaceted nature of the field's response to unprecedented challenges. The intricate interplay between the six overarching thematic domains—research and demography, health and pandemic, education and learning, socio-political responses, geographic and institutional focus, and research nature and publication—underscores the dynamic and interdependent nature of educational research during times of crisis. The collective body of work of these top journals, as evidenced by their impact factors, citations, and network positions, demonstrates a commitment to re-envisioning education in times of crisis. By bringing together diverse disciplinary perspectives, fostering critical conversations, and shedding light on the complex interdependencies that shape the educational landscape during crises, these publications

serve as crucial platforms for fostering resilient, equitable, and socially just educational futures. This thematic analysis contributes to the broader discourse on re-imagining research, teaching, and learning during times of crises, empowering researchers, educators, and policymakers to navigate the challenges and opportunities that lie ahead in the pursuit of a more resilient and equitable educational future.

Discussion, context, limitations, and recommendations

This section delves into a comprehensive discussion of the bibliometric review findings, contextualised within the unique socio-political and economic landscape of Southern Africa. By first examining the specific challenges faced by the region, I provide a solid foundation for analysing the implications of the research findings for educational policy, practice, and future research. The discussion is followed by an acknowledgement of the study's limitations, and concludes with a set of recommendations aimed at fostering resilient, equitable, and socially just education systems in the face of global crises.

Contextualising the challenges in Southern Africa

As highlighted in the literature review, the impact of global crises on education in the Southern African context is further compounded by the region's unique socio-political and economic challenges. Political instability, governance issues, and social inequalities (Rudling et al., 2023) have hindered the development of resilient education systems. Moreover, the economic difficulties faced by Southern African nations, such as widespread poverty, high unemployment rates, and limited resources (World Food Programme, 2022), have exacerbated the effects of crises on education. For instance, the economic fallout of the COVID-19 pandemic has disproportionately affected disadvantaged communities in South Africa, widening the educational gap (Haelermans et al., 2022; Swart et al., 2022). Addressing these socio-political and economic challenges is crucial for building adaptable, inclusive, and equitable education systems in the region. The following discussion section builds on this contextual foundation to analyse the findings of the bibliometric review and their implications for educational research and practice in Southern Africa.

Discussion

The bibliometric review of 5,511 documents has offered profound insights into the landscape of educational research amidst global crises, with a particular focus on the Southern African context. This comprehensive analysis has illuminated the evolution and dynamics of academic discourse from 2000 to 2024, shedding light on how pandemics, wars, economic recessions, and environmental disasters have influenced educational systems. The findings reveal a significant emphasis on the human aspects of crises, educational inequalities, and the urgent need for resilient education systems.

In Southern Africa, the intersection of epistemic injustice, critical pedagogy, and social justice within the realm of educational research has been highlighted as pivotal in addressing and

mitigating the adverse effects of global crises on education. The bibliometric analysis successfully mapped the growth trajectory, dominant themes, and collaborative networks in this field, demonstrating a marked increase in research productivity, particularly in response to recent crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic. This surge in scholarly activity underscores a collective drive towards understanding and overcoming the educational challenges posed by these crises.

Significantly, the review has identified gaps in the literature, especially in the integration of social justice and educational equity into the fabric of resilient educational systems. The research underscores the critical role of education in not only navigating but also transforming the societal landscape in times of crisis. Through the lens of Southern Africa, the studies reviewed have brought to the forefront the complexities and nuances of building education systems that are adaptable, inclusive, and capable of ensuring equitable quality education for all.

Limitations

One limitation of this review is the inherent nature of bibliometric analyses, which focus on quantitative metrics and may not fully capture the depth of qualitative insights into the impact of crises on education. Additionally, the reliance on documents indexed within a specific database might exclude relevant literature not captured by the search criteria, potentially limiting the scope of analysis.

Recommendations

Based on the insights garnered from the bibliometric review, several recommendations emerge for policymakers, educators, and researchers:

- **Enhance policy frameworks:** Develop and implement policy frameworks that are responsive to the evolving nature of global crises and their impact on education, with a focus on safeguarding educational equity and social justice.
- **Foster pedagogical innovation:** Promote pedagogical practices that emphasise critical thinking, problem solving, and adaptability to ensure learners can thrive in uncertain and rapidly changing environments.
- **Strengthen research collaborations:** Encourage interdisciplinary and cross-regional research collaborations to broaden the understanding of crises' impacts on education, and share best practices for resilience and inclusivity.
- **Invest in infrastructure:** Prioritise investment in resilient educational infrastructure and technology to support continuous and accessible learning, especially in under-resourced communities.
- **Support educator development:** Equip educators with the skills and resources needed to navigate the challenges posed by crises, emphasising empathy, equity, and social justice in teaching practices.

By addressing these recommendations, stakeholders could contribute to the development of educational systems that are not only resilient in the face of global crises but also deeply committed to promoting equity, inclusivity, and social justice. This, in turn, would ensure that

education remains a powerful tool for societal transformation and sustainable development, particularly in the Southern African context and beyond.

Conclusion

This research article examined the impact of global crises on education, highlighting a landscape characterised by challenges and possibilities for radical transformation, specifically within the Southern African context. By addressing the unique socio-political and economic challenges faced by the region, the article provides a nuanced understanding of the compounding effects of crises on education systems. The results emphasise the significant importance of education in effectively addressing and navigating the complex barriers presented by crises, emphasising the need to reimagine education systems that possess both resilience and a commitment to equitable and just treatment. The article presents an in-depth review of educational research considering global disruptions, utilising a rigorous bibliometric analysis.

The findings reveal a growing emphasis on the human aspects of crises, educational inequalities, and the urgent need for resilient education systems. By mapping out the growth trajectory, dominant themes, and collaborative networks in this field, the article offers a comprehensive overview of the evolving landscape of educational research amidst global crises. Moreover, the article highlights the intersection of epistemic injustice, critical pedagogy, and social justice within the realm of educational research in Southern Africa. It underscores the critical role of education in not only navigating but also transforming the societal landscape in times of crisis. The review identifies gaps in the literature, particularly in the integration of social justice and educational equity into the fabric of resilient educational systems, providing valuable insights for future research and policy development.

By answering the four research questions posed in the introductory section, this review makes a substantial contribution to the scholarly discourse on education in times of global crises. It sheds light on the approaches that education systems could adopt to adapt to the challenges posed by a swiftly evolving global landscape marked by ongoing crisis. By doing so, it promotes the idea of a future in which education systems possess the ability to endure crises, foster peace, and guarantee sustainable development in accordance with the Sustainable Development Goals. In essence, this paper advocates for a shared dedication to rethinking education in a way that goes beyond traditional boundaries, embracing a more inclusive, caring, and social justice-oriented approach to research, teaching, and learning. By contextualising the findings within the Southern African landscape and providing actionable recommendations, the article contributes to the development of resilient, equitable, and socially just education systems capable of withstanding the challenges posed by global crises.

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